

Special Relativity Pt.1

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Referring to the failure of the Galilean transformation where a particle can move beyond the speed of light, which contradicts Einstein's postulate that no speed can exceed the speed of light. This is demonstrated in the following illustration:

1. A human stands still on Earth (remaining completely stationary, just standing), observing a rocket moving at a speed of $0.9 C$. The rocket then launches a missile with a speed of $0.4 C$ according to its pilot. Now, the question is, what is the speed of the rocket according to an observer on Earth?

Referring to the Galilean transformation, we can determine the velocity of the rocket using the following equation:

$$v_a = v_{\text{Rocket}} + v_{\text{Missile}} = 0.9C + 0.4C = \mathbf{1.3 C}$$

It means that the missile is moving faster than light, violating Einstein's postulate. To explain this, the Galilean transformation is refined by the introduction of the Lorentz transformation.

1. Galilean Transformation

Figure 1: Transformation

Now, let's assume that O' is moving with a velocity v toward the target 'event'.

We can conclude and express the illustration in the following equations:

1. The value of the distance between O and $Event$ is x :

$$x = x' + vt \tag{1}$$

2. The value of the distance between O' and $Event$ is x' :

$$x' = x - vt \tag{2}$$

3. Referring to the Galilean transformation, which states that t' is equal to t :

$$t' = t \tag{3}$$

4. All objects are moving only along the x -axis, therefore:

$$y = y' \tag{4}$$

$$z = z' \tag{5}$$

Now, assume that the 'event' is moving along with O'

Figure 2: Transformation

We can conclude and express the illustration in the following equations:

1. The Distance between O' and $Event$ is :

$$x' = 0 \tag{6}$$

2. The Distance between O and $Event$ is :

$$x = v \times t \tag{7}$$

2. Lorentz Transformation

Between the Galilean transform and the Lorentz transform, they operate in a similar manner.

1. Because the only variables that change during the 'event' are time and linear motion along the X-axis we must use matrix in order to do a transformation

$$\begin{bmatrix} x' \\ t' \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A & B \\ C & D \end{bmatrix} \times \begin{bmatrix} x \\ t \end{bmatrix} \quad (8)$$

$$x' = Ax + Bt \quad (9)$$

$$t' = Cx + Dt \quad (10)$$

2. now substitute (9) with $x' = 0$ and $x = v \times t$

$$x' = Ax + Bt$$

$$0 = A(v \times t) + Bt$$

$$B = -Av \quad (11)$$

3. substitute (9) with (11)

$$x' = Ax + Bt$$

$$x' = Ax - Avt$$

$$x' = A(x - vt) \quad (12)$$

4. Referring to Einstein's second postulate, which explains that the speed of light is always constant.

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = \frac{dx'}{dt'} = \pm c \quad (13)$$

5. substitute (13) with (9) and (10) :

$$dx \times dt' = dx' \times dt$$

$$dx(dCx + dDt) = dt(dAx + dBt)$$

$$d^2Cx^2 + d^2Dtx = d^2Atx + d^2t^2B$$

$$Cx^2 + (D - A)tx - Bt^2 = 0 \quad (14)$$

6. now substitute (14) with $x = \pm c \times t$

- A. if c is positive

$$Cx^2 + (D - A)tx - Bt^2 = 0$$

$$C(c^2t^2) + (D - A)(ct^2) - Bt^2 = 0$$

$$C(c^2) + (D - A)c + Av = 0 \quad (15)$$

B. if c is negative

$$\begin{aligned}
 Cx^2 + (D - A)tx - Bt^2 &= 0 \\
 C(c^2t^2) - (D - A)(ct^2) - Bt^2 &= 0 \\
 C(c^2) - (D - A)c + Av &= 0
 \end{aligned} \tag{16}$$

7. now, eliminate (15) and (16)

$$\begin{array}{r}
 C(c^2) + (D - A)c + Av = 0 \\
 C(c^2) - (D - A)c + Av = 0 \quad - \\
 \hline
 2(D - A)c = 0 \\
 D = A
 \end{array} \tag{17}$$

8. We can use either equation (16) or (15), and substitute it with (17).

$$\begin{aligned}
 C(c^2) - (D - A)c + Av &= 0 \\
 C(c^2) + Av &= 0 \\
 C &= -\frac{Av}{c^2}
 \end{aligned} \tag{18}$$

9. now, substitute (10) with (18) and (17)

$$\begin{aligned}
 t' &= Cx + Dt \\
 t' &= -\left(\frac{Avx}{c^2}\right) + At \\
 t' &= A\left(t - \frac{vx}{c^2}\right)
 \end{aligned} \tag{19}$$

Now, let's switch to a different perspective, where O' is stationary, but O is moving in X-axis with v Velocity

Figure 3: Transformation

referring to the new illustration. now the equation has changed :

10. Since the variables that change are x and t , the transformation in effect now is not x' and t' .

$$\begin{bmatrix} x \\ t \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A & B \\ C & D \end{bmatrix} \times \begin{bmatrix} x' \\ t' \end{bmatrix}$$

$$x = Ax' + Bt' \quad (20)$$

$$t = Cx' + Dt' \quad (21)$$

11. Referring to (20) and the direction of v is negative :

$$\begin{aligned} B &= -Av \\ B &= Av \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

12. substitute (20) with (22),(12) and (19)

$$\begin{aligned} x &= Ax' + Bt' \\ x &= A(Ax - Avt) + (Av) \left(At - \frac{Avx}{c^2} \right) \\ x &= A^2x - A^2vt + A^2vt - \left(\frac{A^2v^2x}{c^2} \right) \\ x &= A^2x - \left(\frac{A^2v^2x}{c^2} \right) \\ 1 &= A^2 - \left(\frac{A^2v^2}{c^2} \right) \\ 1 &= A^2 \left(1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2} \right) \\ A &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}} \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

Here, 'A' is commonly known as the Lorentz factor, denoted by γ

$$A = \gamma \quad (24)$$

Referring to the Lorentz factor, we can derive several equations by substituting the Lorentz factor.

13. first one, we can derive x' :

$$\begin{aligned} x' &= A(x - vt) \\ x' &= \gamma(x - vt) \end{aligned} \quad (25)$$

14. we can derive t' also :

$$\begin{aligned} t' &= A \left(t - \frac{vx}{c^2} \right) \\ t' &= \gamma \left(t - \frac{vx}{c^2} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (26)$$

15. now, we can derivate (25) and (26) to make new equation :

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{dx'}{dt'} &= \frac{\gamma(dx - vdt)}{\gamma\left(dt - \frac{vdx}{c^2}\right)} \\ v'_x &= \frac{\left(\frac{dx}{dt} - \frac{vdt}{dt}\right)}{\left(\frac{dt}{dt} - \frac{vdx}{c^2 dt}\right)} \\ v'_x &= \frac{v_x - v}{1 - \frac{v \times v_x}{c^2}}\end{aligned}\tag{27}$$

16. we can transform it into :

$$v_x = \frac{v'_x + v}{1 + \frac{v'_x \times v}{c^2}}\tag{28}$$

Now, let's fix the answer to our main problem (1).

- 1 A human stands still on Earth (remaining completely stationary, just standing), observing a rocket moving at a speed of 0.9 C. The rocket then launches a missile with a speed of 0.4 C according to its pilot. Now, the question is, what is the speed of the rocket according to an observer on Earth?

$$\begin{aligned}v_x &= \frac{v'_x + v}{1 + \frac{v \times v'_x}{c^2}} \\ v_x &= \frac{0,4C + 0,9C}{1 + \frac{0,4C \times 0,9C}{c^2}} \\ v_x &= \frac{1,3C}{1,36} \\ v_x &\approx 0,955..C\end{aligned}$$

The solution to the problem does not violate any rules especially einstein postulat. This means that the equations we obtained are correct, and simultaneously, we have derived equations regarding relativistic velocity

2 Time Dilation

Now, i have illustration :

Figure 4: Time dilatation

The time required from *Event 1* to *Event 2* is denoted as Δt , and it will have the same value according to both observers, O' or O .

$$\Delta t = t_2 - t_1 \quad (29)$$

$$\Delta t' = t'_2 - t'_1 \quad (30)$$

17. we can substitute (30) with (26) :

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta t' &= t'_2 - t'_1 \\ \Delta t' &= \gamma \left(t_2 - \frac{vx_2}{c^2} \right) - \gamma \left(t_1 - \frac{vx_1}{c^2} \right) \\ \Delta t' &= \gamma (t_2 - t_1) \\ \Delta t' &= \gamma \Delta t \end{aligned} \quad (31)$$

(31) is the final equation of time dilatation.

3 Length Contraction

for Length contraction, actually it has same illustration with time dilatation:

Figure 5: Length Contraction

The distance required from *Event 1* to *Event 2* is denoted as ΔX , and it will have the same value according to both observers, O' and O .

$$\Delta x = x_2 - x_1 \quad (32)$$

$$\Delta x' = x'_2 - x'_1 \quad (33)$$

18. we can substitute (33) with (25)

$$\begin{aligned} x' &= x'_2 - x'_1 \\ x' &= \gamma(x_2 - vt) - \gamma(x_1 - vt) \\ x' &= \gamma(x_2 - x_1) \\ x' &= \gamma\Delta x \end{aligned} \quad (34)$$

(34) is the final equation of length contraction.

4 Mass Relativity

In the theory of special relativity, mass is also relative and depends on the observer. And it can be demonstrated through the Lorentz transformation :

Assume that an observer inside a rocket (O'), moving at a speed approaching the speed of light, is observing two particles colliding and coming to rest. Meanwhile, there is an observer on Earth also observing these two particles.

This is an illustration of what the observer inside the rocket would observe.

Figure 6: Illustration 1

According to observer in the rocket (O'), both particles come to a stop. However, what are the observations from the perspective of an observer on Earth (O)?

This is the illustration of what the observer on the Earth would observe.

Figure 7: Illustration 2

Referring to both illustrations and the law of conservation of momentum, we can formulate an equation :

a . According to O' Observer :

$$m'v' - m'v' = 0 \quad (35)$$

b . According to O Observer :

$$m_1v_1 + m_2v_2 = (m_1 + m_2)v \quad (36)$$

When both particles are in motion, their velocities are relative. Therefore, we can express it as follows:

$$v_1 = \frac{v' + v}{1 + \frac{v' \times v}{c^2}} \quad (37)$$

and

$$v_2 = \frac{-v' + v}{1 - \frac{v' \times v}{c^2}} \quad (38)$$

19. we can substitute (36) with (37) and (38)

$$\begin{aligned} m_1v_1 + m_2v_2 &= (m_1 + m_2)v \\ m_1 \left(\frac{v' + v}{1 + \frac{v' \times v}{c^2}} \right) + m_2 \left(\frac{-v' + v}{1 - \frac{v' \times v}{c^2}} \right) &= m_1v + m_2v \end{aligned} \quad (39)$$

20. To simplify the derivation of the formula, we can use a substitution. assume that $\frac{v' \times v}{c^2}$ is equal to b :

$$\begin{aligned} m_1 \left(\frac{v' + v}{1 + b} \right) - m_1v &= m_2v - m_2 \left(\frac{-v' + v}{1 - b} \right) \\ m_1 \left(\frac{v' + v}{1 + b} - v \right) &= m_2 \left(v - \left(\frac{-v' + v}{1 - b} \right) \right) \\ m_1 \left(\frac{v' + v - v - vb}{1 + b} \right) &= m_2 \left(\frac{v - vb + v' - v}{1 - b} \right) \\ m_1 \left(\frac{v' - vb}{1 + b} \right) &= m_2 \left(\frac{v' - vb}{1 - b} \right) \\ \frac{m_1}{1 + b} &= \frac{m_2}{1 - b} \\ \frac{m_1}{m_2} &= \frac{1 + b}{1 - b} \\ \frac{m_1}{m_2} &= \frac{1 + \frac{v' \times v}{c^2}}{1 - \frac{v' \times v}{c^2}} \end{aligned} \quad (40)$$

21. according to lorentz transformation :

$$\begin{aligned}
1 - \frac{v_1^2}{c^2} &= 1 - \frac{1}{c^2} \left(\frac{v' + v}{1 + \frac{v' \times v}{c^2}} \right)^2 \\
1 - \frac{v_1^2}{c^2} &= \frac{1}{c^2} \left(c + \frac{v' + v}{1 + \frac{v' \times v}{c^2}} \right) \left(c - \frac{v' + v}{1 + \frac{v' \times v}{c^2}} \right) \\
1 - \frac{v_1^2}{c^2} &= \frac{1}{c^2} \left(\frac{v' + v + c + \frac{v' \times v}{c}}{1 + \frac{v' \times v}{c^2}} \right) \left(\frac{-v' - v + c + \frac{v' \times v}{c}}{1 + \frac{v' \times v}{c^2}} \right) \\
1 - \frac{v_1^2}{c^2} &= \frac{1}{c^2} \left(\frac{(c + v) + v' \left(1 + \frac{v}{c}\right)}{1 + \frac{v' \times v}{c^2}} \right) \left(\frac{(c - v) - v' \left(1 - \frac{v}{c}\right)}{1 + \frac{v' \times v}{c^2}} \right)
\end{aligned} \tag{41}$$

22. factorize the equation :

$$\begin{aligned}
1 - \frac{v_1^2}{c^2} &= \frac{1}{c^2} \left(\frac{c \left(1 + \frac{v}{c}\right) + v' \left(1 + \frac{v}{c}\right)}{1 + \frac{v' \times v}{c^2}} \right) \left(\frac{c \left(1 - \frac{v}{c}\right) - v' \left(1 - \frac{v}{c}\right)}{1 + \frac{v' \times v}{c^2}} \right) \\
1 - \frac{v_1^2}{c^2} &= \frac{1}{c^2} \left(\frac{(c + v') \left(1 + \frac{v}{c}\right)}{1 + \frac{v' \times v}{c^2}} \right) \left(\frac{(c - v') \left(1 - \frac{v}{c}\right)}{1 + \frac{v' \times v}{c^2}} \right) \\
1 - \frac{v_1^2}{c^2} &= \frac{1}{c^2} \left(\frac{(c^2 - v'^2) \left(1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}\right)}{\left(1 + \frac{v' \times v}{c^2}\right)^2} \right) \\
1 - \frac{v_1^2}{c^2} &= \left(\frac{\left(1 - \frac{v'^2}{c^2}\right) \left(1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}\right)}{\left(1 + \frac{v' \times v}{c^2}\right)^2} \right)
\end{aligned} \tag{42}$$

23. the equation has similarity with :

$$1 - \frac{v_2^2}{c^2} = \left(\frac{\left(1 - \frac{v'^2}{c^2}\right) \left(1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}\right)}{\left(1 - \frac{v' \times v}{c^2}\right)^2} \right) \tag{43}$$

24. Now, we can try divided (42) by (43)

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{1 - \frac{v_1^2}{c^2}}{1 - \frac{v_2^2}{c^2}} &= \left(\frac{\left(1 - \frac{v'^2}{c^2}\right) \left(1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}\right) \left(1 - \frac{v' \times v}{c^2}\right)^2}{\left(1 + \frac{v' \times v}{c^2}\right)^2 \left(1 - \frac{v'^2}{c^2}\right) \left(1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}\right)} \right) \\
\frac{1 - \frac{v_1^2}{c^2}}{1 - \frac{v_2^2}{c^2}} &= \left(\frac{\left(1 - \frac{v' \times v}{c^2}\right)^2}{\left(1 + \frac{v' \times v}{c^2}\right)^2} \right)
\end{aligned} \tag{44}$$

25. according to (40), we can substitute the (44).

$$\sqrt{\frac{1 - \frac{v_1^2}{c^2}}{1 - \frac{v_2^2}{c^2}}} = \frac{m_2}{m_1} \tag{45}$$

26. referring to (45) and 'figure 7', we can the conclusion that :

1 $v_1 = v_2$

2 $m_1 = m_2$

3 $v_2 = 0 \rightarrow m_2 = m_o$

4 $v_1 = v \rightarrow m_1 = m$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v_1^2}{c^2}}}{1 - 0} &= \frac{m_2}{m_1} \\ m &= \frac{m_0}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}} \\ m &= m_0 \times \gamma \end{aligned} \tag{46}$$

(46) is the *mass relativity* equations.

If mass is relative, does that mean everything related to mass is also relative? Such as force, momentum, work, and other derivatives?